

Supplementary materials

Figure S1.

Figure S1. Production of granzyme B in PBMC exposed to iPS-RPE cells.

For the assay, peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) and human iPS-RPE cells were cultured at different cell numbers (PBMC: RPE ratio= 200:1, 20:1, or 2:1). The evaluation was performed by granzyme B flow cytometry or ELISA showing CTL activity. Panels show flow cytometry, and % numbers in the histogram indicate double-positive cells for CD8/granzyme B. The numbers in parentheses in the histogram indicate granzyme B ELISA (ng/mL) in the supernatants from PBMC plus allogeneic iPS-RPE cells.

Figure S2.

Figure S2. Induction of RPE-specific CTL and ⁵¹Cr release assay.

For induction of RPE-specific CTL, PBMC were co-cultured with x-irradiated iPS-RPE cells (20 Gy) for 7 days with recombinant IL-2 in RPMI with 10% FBS medium (CTL induction phase). After 7 days, harvested PBMC were separated from CD8⁺ T cells, and isolated CD8⁺ T cells were co-cultured with ⁵¹Cr radionuclide-labeled RPE cells. Purified CD8⁺ T cells were incubated with target iPS-RPE cells in the ⁵¹Cr release assay (CTL killing assay).

Table S1. Cytotoxic responses of CD8-positive T cells to human iPS-RPE cells in MHC restriction

Donor	Effector cells	Target cells		
TLHD-2	CD8 ⁺ T cells	TLHD2 iPS-RPE (Auto cells)	Ff-I01 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	B cells (Allo cells: PC)
Granzyme B (pg/mL)	328	389	866	3458
TLHD-23	CD8 ⁺ T cells	TLHD2 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	Ff-I01 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	B cells (Allo cells: PC)
Granzyme B (pg/mL)	99	480	396	2520
STHD-1	CD8 ⁺ T cells	TLHD2 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	253G1 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	B cells (Allo cells: PC)
Granzyme B (pg/mL)	216	2900	900	5450
TLHD-29	CD8 ⁺ T cells	TLHD2 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC mismatched)	Ff-I01 iPS-RPE (Allo cells: MHC matched)	B cells (Allo cells: PC)
Granzyme B (pg/mL)	40	490	116	2347

Numbers in the table indicate the data from human granzyme B ELISA (pg/mL).

Allo cells, allogeneic cells; Auto cells, autogenic cells; PC, positive control cells.